

Effect of Challenges in the TVET Sector on Graduate Employability in the Changing Employment Dynamics in Kenya

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Abstract

This study sought to examine the challenges of the TVET sector in meeting graduate employability in the changing employment dynamics in Kenya. Specific objectives included establishing the influence of institutional objectives, and operational departmental plans of TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya. The study was anchored on resource-based view theory and strategic theory and used descriptive research design focusing on a sample of 353 key management staffs from public and private TVET institutions from the 4 Nairobi metropolitan counties of Nairobi, Machakos, Kiambu and Kajiado. Primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire, and descriptive statistics and thematic methods applied in data analysis. Analyzed data was presented using tables, figures, and narratives. The study noted that institutional objectives and operational departmental plans had significant influence on TVET graduate employability in Kenya. Regarding the influence of institutional objectives in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya, the study concluded that the institutions should always have strong objectives which are clearly aligned to their mission. With a P-value of 0.002 ($p=0.002<0.05$) at 5% level of significance, it was concluded that institutional objectives had a significant influence on graduate employability. Furthermore, operational department plans influenced capacity of TVETs, especially when it comes to specialization and innovativeness. With a P-value of 0.000 ($p=0.000<0.05$) at 5% level of significance, it was concluded that operational departmental plans had a significant influence on institutional improvement for graduate employability. The study recommended that TVET institutions should constantly set clear short-term and long-term goals and objectives which guide them in their strategy review and general development journey as well as create different departments and allocate them sufficient resources for coordinating registration and training of students on specific courses.

Key words: Institutional, operational, employability, employment, TVET

1.0 Introduction

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in Kenya is currently playing a central role in enhancing the imparting of hand-on skills and knowledge in the sector's graduates that are joining the employment industry in different sectors of the economy (Niittylahti et al, 2021). This is because the training offered by TVET institutions enables students to acquire specialized practical knowledge and skills to effectively take up their intended jobs after clearing college, thereby emphasizing the question of employability of the graduates once they hit the job market. However, the extent to which TVET institutions are preparing their students for the job market has continued to be the subject of discussion among employers in different sectors of the economy, not only in Kenya but across different economies of the world (Huismann, 2018).

The capacity of TVET institutions to effectively produce graduates that are ready for the ever-changing employment dynamics may not be guaranteed unless key players in the sector are keen to progressively address current and emerging challenges. According to Hippach-Schneider and Huismann (2019), for the TVET to work in tandem with any country's economic plans, there must be a TVET strategy which outlines a comprehensive policy formulation and operationalization for the greater good of the country in question. Huismann (2018) argues that such a framework should be able to address any emerging challenges of vocational training such that there is constant alignment and realignment of training curriculum, policies and programs to the broader national development, human resource training, poverty reduction/eradication, and wealth creation agenda. Margo et al (2020) reinforce this argument by stating that any strategy review on TVET management must put into consideration employability of the graduates being churned out of the TVET institutions.

In Africa and developing countries in general where there is a relatively big percentage of skilled yet unemployed people, TVET could play a significant role in equipping young people with the necessary skills needed for self-employment (Ngugi, 2019). Despite the importance of TVET in improving the informal job sector by offering the requisite knowledge and skills to millions of young people in the region graduating from high schools into an uncertain job market, there is empirical evidence that TVET education has not been fully embraced as a priority in several developing countries (Gachunga et al., 2020a). Some of the challenges facing TVET education in most Sub-Saharan African countries include the system's inability to progressively address the emerging gaps in the employment subsector due to what has been viewed as rigid training curriculum. The same challenges are experienced in the Kenyan case despite the significant strides the country has recently made in its TVET education and training sector according to the Technical and Vocational Education and Training Authority (TVETA, 2018).

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The growth of the TVET education and training sector in Kenya has no doubt been on an upward trajectory for close to ten years now. From a student population of 148,009 in about 750 TVET colleges in 2013 nationally, statistics indicate that the sector boasts of close to 600,000 students enrolled in more than 2,300 TVET institutions as of last year (Kamer, 2022). This scenario would call for regular review and strengthening of the institutions in order to offer better training to the graduates who continuously join the ever-changing job market both in the national and international scenes. However, the government and other key stakeholders in the TVET industry may not be doing enough to progressively equip graduates with the best skillsets for the job market.

Some of the challenges related to the TVET sector's meeting of graduate employability in the changing employment dynamics in Kenya have to do with institutional objectives and operational departmental plans of TVET institutions. Despite recommendations by previous studies the need to adopt Competence Based Education and Training (CBET) to identify training gaps for more competent TVET graduates, several institutions lack the capacity to regularly conduct strategy reviews to properly align their curricula with the changing job market due to the challenges. This study examined the challenges of the TVET sector in meeting graduate employability in the changing employment dynamics in Kenya.

1.2 Research Objectives

- i. To establish the influence of weak institutional objectives in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya
- ii. To establish the influence of unclear operational departmental plans of TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya.

1.3 Hypotheses of the Study

The study was guided by the following hypotheses:

H₀₁ There is no statistically significant influence of institutional objectives in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya.

H₀₂ There is no statistically significant influence of operational departmental plans of TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Review: Strategic Theory

This study was anchored on strategic theory. Strategic theory was initiated by Tom Burns and G. M. Stalker in 1961 to offer guidance on strategic management of institutions in both public and private sector (Burns & Stalker, 1961). The strategic theory states that strategic management

principles and practices play a central role in determining organizational success. The theory recognizes the importance of creating harmony among different sections of an organization for the sake of tangible performance. The theory proposes the need for periodic and progressive review of strategic factors in order to improve performance of an organization. The same principle may apply to TVET institutions, with the need for unceasing strategy review based on the current and emerging needs in the job market.

Based on strategic theory, Cole-Ingait (2019) argues that apart from strategic factors which can be defined as core factors that the organization needs to get right for its overall success, there is a possibility for some organizations to adopt new strategic factors to propel their success to new heights every time it emerges that they can no longer cope with earlier strategic factors. Strategy review of TVET institutions contemplates new ways of doing things and dismantling of the status quo. This also means a paradigm shift and investment of more resources to enable implementation of the new systems. For instance, the current study envisioned review of institutional objectives, and departmental plans as possible institutional efforts and initiatives by TVET institutions for equipping the graduates with the right skills for the job market.

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Institutional Objectives of TVET on Graduate Employability

Learning institutions are driven partly by the need to produce to the job market responsible and responsive citizens with the desire to create meaningful change in areas of operation (Picatoste et al, 2018). This is no exception to the TVET establishments which are strongly associated with imparting of hands-on skills and knowledge to students that pass through the system. A TVET graduate is ideally expected to be equipped with innovation and leadership skills, with a clear focus on professional excellence based on holistic nurturing and development at personal and career levels (Anwar & Hasnu, 2017). Overall, the objective of the TVET sector is to effectively equip learners with the right training and skills for the labour market in an environment defined by fast evolving employers' requirements from prospective employees (Suleman, 2018). Yet, every TVET institution could be guided by its unique operational needs which determine priorities.

Mumbe (2020) carried out a study on employability skills among TVET students in Kilifi County and revealed that there were several dynamics related to the students' attainment of the right skills from TVET. Involving a target population of 2,564 comprising of principals, instructors, 2nd year trainees and graduates, through purposive and stratified random sampling technique, 300 individuals participated in the study. Key findings of the study indicated that the situation led to disinterest in the training and subsequently caused low enrollment. Despite the efforts by the TVET institutions to prioritize training of students based on the current job market demands, they lacked sufficient training resources and facilities.

High staff turnover due to low remuneration also made it difficult for majority of the TVET colleges to properly execute their mandates. At the same time, several TVET establishments were struggling with limited physical infrastructure, such as classrooms and space for workshops for accommodating of the growing number of new registered students for the TVET programs (Anwar & Hasnu, 2017). However, there was not guarantee of quality teaching by the part-time tutors as there were not clearly established structured for doing background checks on their skills sets before they were hired (Norton, 2018).

Notwithstanding the challenges faced by TVET institutions in Kenya in general, there are still hopes that things could improve regarding training of TVET graduates and imparting them with the right skills for ready and easy employment in the labour market. According to Ochami (2020), TVET graduates still stand better changes of being absorbed into the job market compared to university graduates. Besides employability which dominates the objectives of TVET training, several TVET providers are beginning to adopt the important principles of flexibility, adaptability, and lifelong skills as the hallmark of best practices and foundation for a better equipped TVET graduate.

2.2.2 Operational Departmental Plans of TVET and Graduate Employability

Departmental plans in a training institution refer to individual expenditure plans for each department based on priority training needs (Abdullah et al, 2019), Departmental plans can provide a roadmap on how an institutional department intends to rollout detailed activities over a given period on priority basis and the resources needed to accomplish specific tasks. Like many other training institutions, TVET establishments are required to set their priorities at their smaller units of management, thereby spelling out strategies for accomplishing specific milestones within specified duration of time. However, Abdul and Maat (2019) observed that departmental plans must be accompanied by budgetary allocations, human resource expertise, and timeframe.

According to Ngugi (2019), proper design, review and implementation of department plans help to communicate an institution's main priorities through a strategic outcome, program and expected results. Hence, institutional department plans inform faculty members and students on planned activities and expenditures on different items meant to support effective learning and enhancing the outcome of the overall training. From analyzed primary data collected using a structured questionnaire and processed descriptively and inferentially with the help of SPSS computer software, it was noted that there was a close relationship between departmental management practices and strategic plans implementation.

Despite the practical orientation of curriculum of TVETs' teaching departments, a good number of TVET graduates lacked soft skills needed in the job environment. The survey recommended enhanced public-private partnerships to enable a more holistic approach in equipping TVET graduates with the right skills for the job market. This included implementation of industrial

attachments that expose finalist students to practical skills ahead of their graduation. According to Abdul and Maat (2019), common challenges related to departmental plans in TVET institutions mainly revolved around lack of infrastructure, inferior training equipment and limited physical facilities, and low-quality programs and teaching staff. As a result of these challenges, UNESCO (2020) concluded that careers related to TVET education and training was in jeopardy since most students would consider TVET as their last option for post-secondary education. These views were reiterated by Muthuprasad et al (2021) by noting that TVET institutions can only play their rightful position if they progressively offer more relevant courses to students.

2.3 Conceptual framework

Figure 1 shows a conceptual relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Independent Variables

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted survey research design and used both quantitative and qualitative data for answering the research questions.

3.2 Target Population

The target population for this study constituted Ministry of Education (MOE) officials, and 506 public and private TVET institutions in four Nairobi metropolitan counties of Nairobi, Machakos, Kajiado, and Kiambu. Top management in different operational departments of the 506 TVET institutions was involved in the study, with target population of 3036 individuals.

3.3 Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

The study used stratified random sampling technique to select a representative sample from the target population. The Yamane (1967) formula was used to calculate the sample, as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

where n represented sample size, N population (sampling frame) and e level of precision or margin of error. In this case, N= 3036, hence the sample size will be:

$$n = \frac{3036}{1 + 3036(.05)^2} = 353.$$

Hence, the sample size for the study was 353.

Table 1 Sample Size

Category	Target Population (N)	Sample Size
Principals/Deputy Principals	506	59
Registrars	506	59
Dean of students for academics	506	59
Heads of Departments	1518	176
Total	3036	353

3.4 Research Instruments

A questionnaire was used to collect primary data from the research participants. The questionnaire consisted of close ended and open-ended questions to allow collection of quantitative and qualitative data from the respondents.

3.5 Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaires were administered through face-to-face interviews. However, in some cases, blank questionnaires were left for the respondents to self-administer before the research team could collect completed copies on a later agreed date.

3.6 Data Analysis and Presentation

Data analysis was carried out using descriptive, inferential, and thematic content analysis technique. SPSS version 25 computer software and excel worksheets were used to organize and analyze quantitative data descriptively and inferentially whereas qualitative data was processed by searching across the dataset to identify, analyze and report emerging themes and repeated patterns. Findings were presented using tables, figures, and narratives.

4.0 Results and Discussions

The study involved 301 respondents from TVET institutions from the 4 Nairobi Metropolitan counties of Nairobi, Machakos, Kajiado and Kiambu who were categorized as Principals or Deputy Principals, Registrars, Dean of students for academics, and Heads of Departments.

Table 2 Response Rate

Category	Sample Size	Response Rate	
	Frequency (N)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Principals/Deputy Principals	59	54	92
Registrars	59	53	90
Dean of students for academics	59	51	86
Heads of Departments	176	143	81
Total	353	301	85

The sample was 353, but 301 of the respondents managed to participate in the study by fully completing and returning the questionnaires. This translated into the response rate of 85%.

4.1 Influence of Institutional Objectives in TVET Institutions on Graduate Employability

Institutional objectives, goals, and aspirations of TVET institutions were important aspects of enhancing performance of the institutions.

Figure 2. Clear Institutional Objectives

Based on the statistics in figure 4.8, 96% (288) of the respondents agreed that their respective TVETs had clear institutional objectives, against 4% (13) of them who answered no to this proposition. The statistics can further imply that a greater majority of the TVET establishments are clear in their objectives as they aspire to offer relevant courses to the student fraternity. However, besides having institutional objectives, it was important for these to be relevant in enhancing employability of students when they finally entered the job market. Yet, due to several shortcomings in the TVET sector, the industry is not able to constantly come up with innovative ways of matching training and skills provided to TVET graduates with the emerging employment sector demands, such as lack of financial resources.

Table 3 Rating Quality of Training of Students in TVET Institutions

Quality of training of students	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Very low quality	2	1
Low quality	6	2
Moderate quality	22	7
High quality	98	33
Very high quality	173	57
Total	301	100

As indicated on table 3.24, 3% (8) of the respondents had the opinion that the quality of training was of low quality, 7% (22) moderate, 90% (272) of them thought the quality of training was high. From the statistical distribution above, 90% of the respondents had the view that TVETs' training was of high quality and/or very high quality. Despite the overwhelming affirmation of the quality of training by TVETs, the 10% indifferent and/or contrasting views imply that there is still room for improvement. However, in a general sense, a greater percentage of the respondents had confidence in TVETs' quality of training of students, which then increased their chances of employment in different sectors of the economy. To further validate this view, one of the registrars (R027) interviewed had the following to say:

We usually offer quality training in our college, and this can be attested by good number of graduates we release to the employment market annually with some of them landing very good employment opportunities in various sectors of the economy. The excellent performance recorded annually in both internal and external examinations tells you that the quality of training of our students is commendable. The more our graduates shine in their different career paths out there, the more we are convinced that we are offering them the best quality of training.

The need to undertake strategy review was also encouraged by the kind of feedback TVETs managements were receiving regarding how their graduates excelled in the job market. Furthermore, other TVET institutions took a lot of pride in their highly qualified doctorate and master's degree holder tutors they had in their various fields of specialization. It further emerged that TVETs' management was generally keen on ensuring high quality training, encouraged by the referrals they often received from employers.

Previous studies related to Africa and other developing countries in general showed that there is relatively big a percentage of skilled yet unemployed people. According to Ngugi (2019) and Ajithkumar (2017), such a scenario can be addressed through more rigorous and focused training in the TVET sector. In this sense, TVET will play a significant role in equipping young people with the necessary skills needed for self-employment. The move can also help to address the problem of declining opportunities in the formal employment sector while at the same time enabling economies in the region to avoid overdependence on salaried jobs. Despite the important place of TVET in improving the informal job sector through robust knowledge and skills to

millions of young people in the region graduating from high schools, like Gachunga et al. (2020a) noted, the findings of the current research revealed that many developing countries including Kenya, have not fully embraced as a priority.

4.2 Influence of TVETs’ Operational Departmental Plans on Graduate Employability

The second objective of the study was to establish the influence of operational departmental plans of TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya. Departmental plans are essential in helping managers to prioritize activities and align them with the overall goals and objectives of an organization. The plans are also essential in setting standards for assessing performance of the organization. Within the context of strategy review of TVET institutions, operational departmental plans can enable the institution to understand the needs of students within the framework of relevant skills for the employment market (Ngugi, 2019).

According to Gachunga et al (2020a), regular review of current departmental programs being offered by TVET institutions has the benefit of keeping the sector relevant to the job market. It is expected that such reviews will commonly point out existing gaps in skills and knowledge, thus pushing institutions to offer what best suits the employment market. Yet, often, the TVET sector is hampered by a lack of sufficient budgetary allocations to offer innovative courses to its graduates. There is also the question of outdated learning policies and curriculum for TVET programs across different neighboring countries, which makes it difficult for implementing harmonized long-term careers for students pursuing TVET courses (Abdullah et al (2019).

On whether different institutions had independent departmental plans that were geared towards enhancing employability of TVET graduates, the findings were illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3 Institution’s Independent Departmental Plans

Figure 3 shows that 69% (209) of the TVET institutions had independent departmental plans, while 31% (92) of said they did not have. These statistics may be informed by the fact that a greater majority of the TVETs in Nairobi metropolitan counties which were involved in the study

belonged to the private sector, with several of them operating as consolidated businesses as opposed to elaborate institutions with distinct operational departments. The fact that more than 30% of these institutions operated as single blocs of business entities may imply that they were constrained in terms of innovative key decisions that could propel them to greater performance.

Recent surveys (Ngugi, 2019; Ogwengo & Osano, 2017) undertaken to assess the role of TVETs in more than 15 countries in Africa established different departments were commonly targeted in this education model. These included the agriculture, public health, and water resource as well as the energy sectors. Others included management of the environment, ICT, and good public sector governance, among others. Following existing gaps in terms of skills and knowledge in these sectors, the studies recommended development of competency-based curriculum to enable students in strategic fields to take TVET programmes as core or compulsory subjects. These findings were reinforced by the current research. Equally rated as very critical TVET sector development were handicrafts, computer literacy, and entrepreneurship courses. However, liked it emerged in this study, Gachunga et al (2020a) noted that lack of adequate resources, common learning policies and curriculum for TVET programs across different neighboring countries made it difficult for implementing a harmonized long terms career for students pursuing TVET courses.

4.3 Regression Analysis and Testing of Hypotheses

Regression analysis was carried out to understand the relationship between the predictor variables and the dependent variable, and test hypotheses of the study. Multiple linear regression analysis helped the researcher to better understand the outcome of the two predictor variables when they are put in a combined relationship. It was also essential in increasing reliability of each of the variables when it comes to their contribution on the outcome of the study by avoiding overdependence on just one variable but rather consider both the independent variables in looking at their support to the dependent variable. Multiple regression analysis also helped or permitted the researcher to test the hypotheses pursued in the research. In this case, the multiple linear regression model was adopted for testing the significance of the influence of strategy review (independent or predictor variable) on employability (dependent variable or outcome of the study) of TVET graduates.

Table 4 Multiple Regression Coefficients

Predictor	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	β	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	2.880	0.525		5.481	0.000
X1 Institutional objectives	0.125	0.094	0.079	1.340	0.002
X2 Operational departmental plans	0.193	0.075	0.154	2.567	0.000

a. Graduate employability

Based on the statistics in table 4, the overall model for the study was $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon$, where Y = graduate employability which was the dependent variable or outcome of the study and X_s are the independent variables where X_1 = institutional objectives, while X_2 = operational departmental plans, ε is the error term, and β was the coefficient of the model. The findings of the multiple regression coefficients further indicated that at the significance level of 0.05, institutional objectives had statistically significant (p-value of 0.002) influence on graduate employability. Same applied to operational departmental plans with a p-value of 0.011, which is less than 0.05, implied a statistically significant relationship on the outcome of the research (employability of TVET graduates). The implication here is that when all the two variables interact together then departmental plans takes the role of institutional objective.

Table 5 Model Summary for TVET Sector Challenges and Graduate Employability

Model	R	R Square (R2)	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.551	.303	.241	.6012

The model summary in table 5 indicates the coefficient (R) was 0.551, which implied there was a correlation between institutional objectives and operational departmental plans, and graduate employability. The statistics further indicated that the coefficient of determination R square (R2) was 0.303 which meant that 30.3% of TVET graduate employability in Kenya was explained by the two factors. ANOVA of the regression model was also carried out to test the good of fit of the model of the study and establish the significance level of the correlation between institutional objectives and operational departmental plans, and graduate employability.

Table 6 ANOVA for TVET Sector Challenges and Graduate Employability

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	19.697	1	19.70	30.28	.003 ^b
Residual	194.515	299	0.65		
Total	214.212	300			

The ANOVA analysis in table 6 shows that the P-value was 0.003 and the *F* statistic (1, 299) at 95% level of significance (0.65) which was less than *F* calculated (30.28). Since the p-value was less than 0.05 ($p=0.003<0.05$), therefore institutional objectives and operational departmental plans had a significant influence on TVET graduate employability.

4.4 Testing the Hypothesis

The first objective of the study was to establish the influence of institutional objectives in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya. Hence, the following null hypothesis was formulated and tested.

H₀₁ There is no statistically significant influence of institutional objectives in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya.

From the findings in table 4 on multiple regression coefficients, we rejected our null (*H₀*) hypothesis that there is no significant influence of institutional objectives in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya. Hence, we adopted alternate hypothesis that there is significant influence of institutional objectives in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya.

The second objective of the study was to establish the influence of operational departmental plans in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya. Hence, the following null hypothesis was formulated and tested.

H₀₂ There is no significant influence of operational departmental plans in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya.

From the foregoing findings in table 4 on multiple regression coefficients, we therefore reject our null (*H₀*) hypothesis that there is no significant influence of operational departmental plans in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya. Hence, we adopt alternate hypothesis that there is significant influence of operational departmental plans in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya.

5.0 Conclusions

Regarding the influence of institutional objectives in TVET institutions on graduate employability in Kenya, the study concluded that the institutions should always have strong objectives which are

clearly aligned to their mission. This will enable the institutions to remain focused and remain true to their values as they advance to the dynamic and unpredictable future in the employment sector. Furthermore, as reflected in table 4, with the P-value of 0.002 which was less than 0.05 ($p=0.002<0.05$) at 5% level of significance, it was concluded that institutional objectives had a significant influence on graduate employability.

The study further concluded that operational department plans are very essential in influencing capacity of TVETs, especially when it comes to specialization and innovativeness. Well-resourced departments are essential in coming up with innovative courses and training programmes that are aligned with the job demands. It also becomes easy to coordinate learning and training activities through different departments as opposed to when dealing with so many different issues in an institution through one single congested operational unit. As indicated in table 4, with the P-value of 0.000 which was less than 0.05 ($p=0.000<0.05$) at 5% level of significance, it was concluded that operational departmental plans had a significant influence on institutional improvement for graduate employability.

6.0 Recommendations

Regarding the influence of institutional objectives, TVET institutions should constantly set clear short-term and long-term goals and objectives which guide them in their strategy review and general development journey. They should also be flexible in terms of setting their priorities based on those objectives and availability of resources for implementation of the same. Even when reviewing courses to be offered, the institutions should not lose the bigger picture of institutional objectives. Also, TVET institutions should be willing to create different departments and allocate them sufficient resources for coordinating registration and training of students on specific courses. This move will be essential in encouraging professionalism and specialization in training of the students as they prepare to later join the job market in different subsectors of the economy.

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